

DRUG SOLUBILITY IMPORTANCE AND ENHANCEMENT TECHNIQUES

***Mrs. Jyoti Kumari**

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, A and E College of Pharmacy,
Mohiuddinnagar, Samastipur, Bihar.

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*Corresponding Author

Mrs. Jyoti Kumari

Assistant Professor, Faculty of
Pharmaceutical Sciences, A and E
College of Pharmacy,
Mohiuddinnagar, Samastipur, Bihar.

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ABSTRACT

Solubility, is defined as the maximum amount of solute dissolve in solvent at particular temperature and pressure. It is one of the most important criteria for the achievement of optimum concentration of drug in blood for desired (anticipated) therapeutic action. Low solubility is the vital problem found in formulation, manufacture, compounding and development of new drug also in development of generic medicine. More than 40% NCEs (new chemical entities) manufactured in pharmaceutical industries are practically proven that are insoluble in water. Solubility is a vital challenge for development scientist. A medicine to be absorbed must be present in the form of solution at biological membrane different approaches are applied for induce the solubility of poorly soluble drugs which are shape, size (Physical) and chemical nature of drug and other methods like particle size reduction

which increase the surface area of drug, crystal engineering, salt formation, solid dispersion, use of surfactant, which reduce the surface area of particles and complexation, Selection of solubility improving techniques depends on drug nature, site of absorption, and needed dosage form characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

Solubility is defined as solid, liquid, or gaseous chemical substance called *solute* to dissolve in a solid, liquid, or gaseous solvent at particular temperature and pressure to form a homogeneous solution of the solute in the solvent. The solubility of a substance basically

depends on the solvent used as well as on temperature and pressure. The extent of solubility of a substance in a specific solvent is measured as the saturation concentration where adding more solute does not increase its concentration in the solution.^[1]

The solvent is mostly a liquid, which can be in a pure form or a mixture of two liquids. mainly the solubility are of two types one which completely soluble (fully miscible) such as ethanol in water, and other one is poorly soluble, such as silver chloride in water. The term *insoluble* is often applied to poorly or very poorly soluble compounds.^[2]

Don't be confused solubility is not only the ability to dissolve a substance, it is the processes may occur not only because of dissolution but also because of a chemical reaction. For example, zinc is insoluble in hydrochloric acid, but does dissolve in it by chemically reacting into zinc chloride and hydrogen, where zinc chloride is soluble in hydrochloric acid. Solubility does not also depend on particle size or other *kinetic* factors; given enough time, even large particles will eventually dissolve.^[3]

Oral route of drug administration is the easy and conventional way of administration because of its convenience and ease of digestion, but for many of the drugs it can be hard way to administer the drug by oral route due to its poor solubility because of lipophilic nature of biological membrane hence will achieve poor bioavailability. Solubility of drug substance is directly proportional to the rate of dissolution according to NoyesWhitney equation solubility is an important parameter for better bioavailability. Pharmacological effectiveness of a medicine depends upon the dissolution, bioavailability and it ultimately depend upon the solubility of drug molecules. Solubility is one of the crucial ways to achieve more amount of medicine in blood and hence it can be defined as amount of solute present in a saturated solution at a constant temperature and pressure in qualitative terms, and in another words can be describe as the spontaneous interaction two or more substances to form a homogeneous molecular dispersion. Only 8% of new drugs in the world have both high solubility and permeability.^[4,5] General definition of different solubility terms are given in the table 1.^[4,6]

Table 1: Definitions of Solubility.

Descriptive terms	Approximate volume of solvent in milliliters per gram of solute
Very soluble	Less than 1
Freely soluble	From 1 to 10
Soluble	From 10 to 30
Sparingly soluble	From 30 to 100

Slightly soluble	From 100 to 1000
Very slightly soluble	From 1000 to 10,000
Insoluble	More than 10,000

Solubility is one of the major approach to get required concentration of drug in blood for achieving better therapeutic result. Poorly or low water (aqueous) soluble drugs mostly needed high doses to achieve therapeutic plasma post oral administration. Less aqueous solubility is a crucial problem found with formulation development and manufacture of new medicine as well as generic drug development. Any medicine for absorption must be needed an aqueous solution form at the target site. Water is the most convince choice for liquid pharmaceutical formulations. Maximum drug is basically acidic or weekly basic in nature having poor aqueous solubility. More than 40% NCEs (new chemical entities) developed in pharmaceutical industry are practically proven that are insoluble in water these poorly water soluble drug absorption leads less and variable bioavailability and gastrointestinal mucosal toxicity. For oral administration drugs solubility is crucial rate limiting parameter to get required amount in blood for therapeutic response. Problem of solubility is a major challenge for formulation scientist.^[7,8]

Process of Solubilization^[9,10]

- **Step 1** - It includes the breaking of inter- ionic or intermolecular force of attraction in the solute, the breakdown of the intermolecular force of attraction between the solvent and the solute molecule or ion.
- **Step 2** - A solid molecule separates from the bulk.
- **Step 3** - It involves integrating the feed of the solid molecule into the hole in the solvent.

Methods for solubility enhancement

When in aqueous media solubility of drug is limited, there are various techniques to improve the solubility of poorly soluble drug (Figure1). There are some traditional and novel techniques to increase the solubility are^[11]:

Figure 1: Broad Classification of Solubility Enhancement Methods.

1. Physical Modification

I. Particle Size Reduction

- Micronization
- Nano suspension

II. Modification of Crystal Habit

- Polymorphs
- Pseudo polymorphs

III. Drug Dispersion in Carrier

- Solid solutions
- Solid dispersions

IV. Solubilization by Surfactants

- Micro emulsion
- Self-micro emulsifying drug delivery system

V. Complexation

2. Chemical modification

I. Hydro trophy

II. Co-solvency

III. Nanotechnology

IV. Salt formation

3. pH adjustment

4. Supercritical fluid process

5. Liquisolid methods

1. Physical Modification

I. Particle Size Reduction

The solubility of drug is mostly intrinsically related to drug particle size; as we decrease the size of particle, the surface area and volume ratio increases. The larger surface area allows greater interaction with the solvent which is responsible for increase in solubility.

Conventional methods of particle size reduction, such as Comminution and spray drying, rely upon mechanical stress to disaggregate the active compound. Particle size reduction is thus allows an efficient, reproducible, and cost effective means of solubility improvement. However, the mechanical forces inherent to apply such as milling and grinding, often impart significant amounts of physical stress upon the drug product which may induce degradation. The thermal stress which may occur during Comminution and spray drying is also a concern when processing thermo sensitive or unstable active compounds. Using traditional approaches for nearly insoluble drugs may not be able to increase the solubility up to desired level.

- **Micronisation:** it is another conventional technique used for reduce the particle size. Micronization enhance the dissolution rate of drugs by increased the surface area, it does not increase equilibrium solubility. Decreasing the particle size of these drugs, which responsible for increase in surface area, improve their rate of dissolution. Micronization of drugs is proceed by milling techniques using jet mill, rotor stator colloid mills and so forth micronization is not beneficial for drugs having a high dose number because it does not change the saturation solubility of the drug.^[12]

These processes were applied to progesterone, fenofibrate, Griseofulvin, spironolactone & diosmin. For these drugs, improved their bioavailability, digestive absorption & clinical efficacy.^[13]

Advantages

- We get uniform particle with small particle size distribution and increase in surface area.

Disadvantages

- High energy process, causes degradation in drug crystal lattice and in the final product amorphous or disordered regions is present.
- Disordered/Amorphous regions are thermodynamically unstable and upon storage in hot and humid conditions these are susceptible to recrystallization.^[13,14]

- **Nano suspension:** This technology is used to poorly soluble drugs that are insoluble in water & oils. Nanosuspension is biphasic system which consists nano size particle in aqueous vehicle. For parenteral and Pulmonary administration or oral and topical use nano size drug particles are stabilized by surfactant. In nano suspension, particle size distribution of solid particle is usually less than one micron. And average particle size range is 200 and 600nm. This process applied to tarazepide, atovaquone, amphotericin & paclitaxel and buparvaquone. Various methods for nanosuspension preparation include Nanocrystals, DissoCubes, Nanopore and Nano edge.^[15]

Advantages

- Size of drug particles is reduced which increase the surface area, which in turn increase dissolution, solubility & bioavailability.
- Nano suspension increase drug permeability.
- Nano suspension increase duration of action of residence.
- Nano suspension increase bio adhesion of drug.
- It exerts advantage of high drug loading.
- Avoidance of organic solvent.

Disadvantage

The main problem suffer in nanosuspension is instability due to crystal growth, agglomeration, Ostwald ripening.^[16]

II. Modification of crystal habit

a) Polymorphs

b) Pseudo polymorphs

Polymorphism is defined as the ability of a solid material to found in two or more different crystalline forms with different arrangements in crystal lattice. Polymorphs are different crystalline forms. Crystalline forms of drugs are chemically same but they have different physiochemical properties like melting point, texture, density, solubility, stability. Similarly, amorphous form of drug is more suitable than crystalline form. Due to more surface area and high associated energy.^[17]

Order of different solid form of drugs.

Amorphous > Metastable polymorphs > Stable polymorphs.

III. Solid dispersion

The concept of solid dispersions was originally proposed by Sekiguchi and Obi, who investigated the generation and dissolution performance of eutectic melts of a sulfonamide drug and a water-soluble carrier in the early 1960s.^[18] Solid dispersions represent a useful pharmaceutical technique for increasing the dissolution, absorption, and therapeutic efficacy of drugs in dosage forms. The term solid dispersion refers to a group of solid products consisting of at least two different components, generally a hydrophilic matrix and a hydrophobic drug. The most commonly used hydrophilic carriers for solid dispersions include polyvinylpyrrolidone (Povidone, PVP), polyethylene glycols (PEGs), Plasdone-S630. Surfactants like Tween-80, docusate sodium, Myrj-52, Pluronic-F68, and sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) also find a place in the formulation of solid dispersion.

The solubility of celecoxib, halofantrine, and ritonavir can be improved by solid dispersion using suitable hydrophilic carriers like celecoxib with povidone (PVP) and ritonavir with gelucire. Various techniques to prepare the solid dispersion of hydrophobic drugs with an aim to improve their aqueous solubility are listed here.^[19,20]

a) Hot-Melt Method (Fusion Method)

b) Solvent Evaporation Method

c) Hot-Melt Extrusion

a) Hot-Melt Method (Fusion Method)

The main benefit of this direct melting method is it's a easy and cost effective. The melting or fusion method was first proposed by Sekiguchi and Obi to prepare fast release solid dispersion dosage forms. In this method, the physical mixture of a drug and a water-soluble carrier are heated directly until the two melts. The melted mixture is then cooled and solidified rapidly in an ice bath with continuous stirring. Then reduce the size of final mass, pulverized, and sieved, which can be compressed into tablets with the help of tableting agents. The melting point of a binary system is dependent upon its composition, that is, the selection of the carrier and the weight fraction of the drug in the system.^[21]

An important requisite for the formation of solid dispersion by the hot-melt method is the miscibility of the drug and the carrier in the molten form. Another important requisite is the thermo stability of both the drug and the carrier.

b) Solvent Evaporation Method

Tachibana and Nakamura^[22] were the first to dissolve both the drug and the carrier in a common solvent and then evaporate the solvent under vacuum to produce a solid solution. This enabled them to produce a solid solution of the highly lipophilic β -carotene in the highly water soluble carrier povidone. Many investigators studied solid dispersion of meloxicam, naproxen, and nimesulide using solvent evaporation technique. These findings suggest that the above-mentioned technique can be employed successfully for improvement and stability of solid dispersions of poorly water soluble drugs.^[12,23]

The benefit of the solvent evaporation method is that thermal decomposition of drugs or carriers can be prevented because of the low temperature needed for the evaporation of organic solvents. However, the disadvantages associated with this method are costly, the difficulty in completely removing the organic solvent (a regulatory perspective), the possible adverse effect of the supposedly negligible amount of the solvent on the chemical stability of the drug, the selection of a common volatile solvent, and the difficulty in reproducing crystal forms.^[24]

c) Hot-Melt Extrusion

Hot-melt extrusion is essentially the same as the fusion method except that intense mixing of the components is induced by the extruder. Just like in the traditional fusion process, miscibility of the drug and the matrix could be a problem. High-shear forces resulting in high local temperature in the extruder is a problem for heat sensitive materials. However, compared to the traditional fusion method, this technique offers the possibility of continuous production, which makes it suitable for large-scale production. Furthermore, the product is easier to handle because at the outlet of the extruder the shape can be adapted to the next processing step without grinding.^[25]

IV. Solubilization by Surfactants

a) Micro emulsion

b) Self-micro emulsifying drug delivery system

(a) Micro emulsion

A hydrophilic surfactant and a hydrophilic solvent mix to dissolve a poorly water-soluble drug in an optically transparent pre-concentrate. The ideal surfactant to be needed. It produces a transparent emulsion of small, homogeneous oil droplets containing the poorly

soluble drug that has been solubilized. Numerous drugs that are completely insoluble in water have been made more soluble by the use of micro emulsions. An oil-in-water microemulsion is the best formulation because it increases solubility by permitting molecules with low water solubility to dissolve into the oil phase. Oral bioavailability can be induced as a result of surfactant-induced permeability alterations.

Advantages of Micro emulsions

- Simplicity of preparation, clarity, ability to be filtered and incorporate a wide range of drugs of varying solubility.^[26]

(b) Self-Micro Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SMEDDS)

The self-emulsifying drug delivery system is made up of a transparent isotropic solution, which is a mixture of oil, surfactant, co-surfactant, one or more hydrophilic solvents and a co-solvent. Oil-in-water micro emulsions are produced by the Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) and Self-micro emulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS), which are isotropic solutions of oil and surfactant. When taken orally, these novel colloidal formulations act like micro emulsions of oil in water.

V. Complexation

Among all the solubility enhancement techniques, inclusion complex formation technique has been employed more precisely to improve the aqueous solubility, dissolution rate, and bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs.

Inclusion complexes are formed by the insertion of the nonpolar molecule or the nonpolar region of one molecule (known as guest) into the cavity of another molecule or group of molecules (known as host). The most commonly used host molecules are cyclodextrins. The enzymatic degradation of starch by cyclodextrin-glycosyltransferase (CGT) produces cyclic oligomers, Cyclodextrins (CDs). These are nonreducing, crystalline, water soluble, and cyclic oligosaccharides consisting of glucose monomers arranged in a donut shaped ring having hydrophobic cavity and hydrophilic outer surface as illustrated in Figure 2. Three naturally occurring CDs are α -Cyclodextrin, β -Cyclodextrin, and γ -Cyclodextrin.^[27]

Figure 2.

Representations of hydrophobic cavity and hydrophilic outer surface of cyclodextrin.^[28]

The surface of the cyclodextrin molecules makes them water soluble, but the hydrophobic cavity provides a microenvironment for appropriately sized non-polar molecules. Based on the structure and properties of drug molecule it can form 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 drug cyclodextrin complex as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: (a).

1 : 1 and 1 : 2 drug cyclodextrin complexes.^[29]

Figure 3: (b).

1 : 1 and 1 : 2 drug cyclodextrin complexes.^[29]

Various technologies adapted to prepare the inclusion complexes of poorly water soluble drugs with cyclodextrins are briefly described below.

a) Kneading Method

This method is based on impregnating the CDs with little amount of water or hydroalcoholic solutions to convert into a paste. The drug is then added to the above paste and kneaded for a specified time. The kneaded mixture is then dried and passed through a sieve if required. In laboratory scale, kneading can be achieved by using a mortar and pestle. In large scale, kneading can be done by utilizing the extruders and other machines. This is the most common and simple method used to prepare the inclusion complexes and it presents very low cost of production.^[30]

b) Lyophilization/Freeze-Drying Technique

In order to get a porous, amorphous powder with high degree of interaction between drug and CD, lyophilization/freeze drying technique is considered suitable. In this technique, the solvent system from the solution is eliminated through a primary freezing and subsequent drying of the solution containing both drug and CD at reduced pressure. Thermo labile substances can be successfully made into complex form by this method. The limitations of this technique is the use of specialized equipment, time consuming process, and yield poor flowing powdered product. Lyophilization/freeze drying technique is considered as an alternative to solvent evaporation and involve molecular mixing of drug and carrier in a common solvent.^[31]

c) Microwave Irradiation Method

This technique involves the microwave irradiation reaction between drug and complexing agent using a microwave oven. The drug and CD in definite molar ratio are dissolved in a mixture of water and organic solvent in a specified proportion into a round-bottom flask. The mixture is reacted for short time of about one to two minutes at 60°C in the microwave oven. After the reaction completes, adequate amount of solvent mixture is added to the above reaction mixture to remove the residual uncomplexed free drug and CD. The precipitate so obtained is separated using whatman filter paper, and dried in vacuum oven at 40°C. Microwave irradiation method is a novel method for industrial scale preparation due to its major advantage of shorter reaction times and higher yield of the product.^[32]

2. Chemical modification

I. Hydro trophy

Hydro trophy is a Solubilization technique, where addition of a large amount of second solute, the hydro tropic agent results in an increase in the aqueous solubility of first solute. Hydro tropic agents are ionic organic salts, contain of alkali metal salts of various organic acids. Additives or salts that increase solubility in given solvent are said to “salt in” the solute and those salts that decrease solubility “salt out” the solute. Several salts with large anions or cations that are themselves very soluble in water result in “salting in” of non electrolytes called “hydro tropic salts”; a phenomenon known as “hydro tropism.” Hydro trophy designate the increase in solubility in water due to the presence of large amount of additives. The mechanism by which it improves solubility is more closely related to complexation involving a weak interaction between the hydro tropic agents like sodium benzoate, sodium acetate, sodium alginate, urea, and the poorly soluble drugs.^[33,34]

The hydro tropes are known to self-assemble in solution. The classification of hydro tropes on the basis of molecular structure is difficult, since a wide variety of compounds have been reported to exhibit hydro tropic behaviour. Specific examples may include ethanol, aromatic alcohols like resorcinol, pyrogallol, catechol, α and β -naphthols and salicylates, alkaloids like caffeine and nicotine, ionic surfactants like diacids, SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate), and dodecylated oxidibenzene. The aromatic hydro tropes with anionic head groups are mostly studied compounds. They are large in number because of isomerism and their effective hydro trope action may be due to the availability of interactive pi (π) orbital.^[35]

Hydro tropes with cationic hydrophilic group are rare, for example salts of aromatic amines, such as procaine hydrochloride. Besides enhancing the solubilization of compounds in water, they are known to exhibit influences on surfactant aggregation leading to micelle formation, phase manifestation of multicomponent systems with reference to nanodispersions and conductance percolation, clouding of surfactants and polymers, and so forth.^[36]

II. Co-solvency

A drug whose solubility in water is weak can have its solubility increased by the use of co-solvents, which are watermiscible solvents in which the drug has a high solubility. Co-Solvents are liquid solutions of one or more water-miscible solvents and water that improve the solubility of insoluble substances. Cosolvent techniques may be suitable for poorly soluble compounds that are lipophilic or highly crystalline and have a high solubility in the

solvent mixture. Cosolvents have the ability to increase the solubility of weakly soluble compounds by thousands of times when compared to the drug's water solubility alone. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylacetamide (DMA) have been used extensively as cosolvents due to their significant solubilization capacity for drugs that are difficult to dissolve and low toxicity.^[37] Weak electrolytes and nonpolar molecules frequently have poor water solubility. These types of solutes are more soluble in a mixture of solvents than in one solvent alone. This phenomenon is known as co-solvency; and the solvents that, in combination increases the solubility of the solute are called co-solvents.

E.g- Phenobarbitone is insoluble in water. A clear solution is obtained by dissolving in mixture of Alcohol, Glycerin and Propylene glycol. This process of improving solubility of solute by addition of combination of solvents is known as cosolvency and the solvent used is known as co-solvents. Examples of commonly used co-solvents are ethanol, sorbitol, glycerin, propylene glycol, polyethylene glycol, etc.

Advantages

- It offers a high solubilization capacity for drugs that are poorly soluble and is simple to formulate, produce and evaluate.

Disadvantages

- As with other excipients, it is important to take into account the toxicity and tolerance of the given solvent level.
- As with all solubilized forms, the insoluble material has lower chemical stability when compared to a crystalline state.^[38]

III. Nanotechnology

The study and use of materials and structures at the nanoscale level of around 100 nanometres (nm) or less is referred to as nanotechnology. Oral bioavailability increase via Micronization is insufficient for many new chemical entities with limited solubility because micronized products have a relatively small effective surface area for dissolving, hence the next stage was nanonization.^[39]

Advantages

It leads to the development of nano or micro sized spherical particles with smooth surfaces, narrow particle size distributions, and large specific surface areas, which increases the dissolving rate and solubility.^[40]

Disadvantages

- The problem of agglomeration is basic and difficult to resolve.^[41]

IV. Salt formation

An API is frequently unable to be created in its purest form because of different instability problems. This conversion results in the formation of salts, cocrystals, solvates, hydrates and polymorphs. Poorly soluble drug candidates (weak acids and bases) have been improved through salt formation. Salts are produced when a substance ionises in solution. It works well in solid dosage forms as well as parenteral and other liquid formulations. When an acidic or basic medication is converted into a salt with a higher solubility than the basic medicine, a salt is formed. E.g- Diclofenac is insoluble in water but Diclofenac sodium is soluble in water.^[42,43]

3. pH adjustment

A drug that is poorly water soluble may be able to dissolve in water if the pH is changed. The buffer capacity and tolerability of the chosen pH must be considered when obtaining solubility using this method.^[44] Excipients that increase the pH of the environment within the dosage form to a level higher than the pKa of weakly acidic pharmaceuticals increase the drug's solubility; excipients that function as alkalizing agents may increase the solubility of weakly basic drugs. It can be used on crystalline and lipophilic poorly soluble substances as well.^[45]

Advantages

- Formulation and analysis both are simple.
- Small amounts of chemical are used, making it ideal for high-throughput testing.^[46]

Disadvantages

- Tolerance and toxicity (both local and systemic) associated with non-physiological pH and extreme pH.

- When diluted in aqueous fluid with a pH lower than the compound's solubility, there is a chance of precipitation. This can create emboli intravenously, and it can also cause variability when taken orally.^[47]

4. Supercritical fluid process

Another novel nanosizing and solubilisation technology whose application has increased in recent years is particle size reduction via supercritical fluid (SCF) processes. Supercritical fluids are fluids whose temperature and pressure are greater than its critical temperature (T_c) and critical pressure (T_p), allowing it to assume the properties of both a liquid and a gas. At near-critical temperatures, SCFs, are highly compressible allowing moderate changes in pressure to greatly alter the density and mass transport characteristics of the fluid that largely determine its solvent power. Once the drug particles are solubilised within the SCF (usually carbon dioxide), they may be recrystallised at greatly reduced particle sizes. The flexibility and precision offered by SCF processes allows micronisation of drug particles within narrow ranges of particle size, often to submicron levels. Current SCF processes have demonstrated the ability to create nanoparticulate suspensions of particles 5–2,000 nm in diameter. Several pharmaceutical companies, such as Nektar Therapeutics and Lavipharm, are specializing in particle engineering via SCF technologies for particle size reduction and solubility enhancement. Several methods of SCF processing have been developed to address individual aspects of these shortcomings, such as precipitation with compressed antisolvent process (PCA), solution enhanced dispersion by SCF (SEDS), supercritical antisolvent processes (SAS), rapid expansion of supercritical solutions (RESS), gas anti solvent recrystallization (GAS), and aerosol supercritical extraction system (ASES).^[48,49]

5. Liquisolid methods

Both absorption and adsorption happen when a drug dissolved in a liquid vehicle is introduced to a carrier material with a porous surface and fibres inside, like cellulose. Specifically, the liquid first absorbs into the interior of the particles and is captured by their internal structure; once this system reaches saturation, the liquid is adsorbed onto the internal and external surfaces of the porous carrier particles. A liquid drug can be transformed into a dry, non-adherent, freeflowing, compressible powder by blending it with specific powder excipients, like the carrier and coating material. Microcrystalline and amorphous cellulose, as well as silica powders, are used as coating materials.^[49,50]

Advantages

- Used in the production of liquid or oil-based drugs.
- Different carriers and additives, such as PVP, PEG 6000, Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose and Eudragit, among others, can be used to modify drug release.
- Improves the bioavailability and solubility of water-insoluble medications when administered orally.
- A variety of drugs with poor solubility can be formulated into the system.
- This system is specifically designed for powdered liquid drugs.^[51]

Disadvantages

- For large doses of insoluble drugs (>100 mg), it is not applicable.
- It requires recipients with strong adsorption and specific surface area characteristics.^[52]

CONCLUSION

Solubility is one of the most important parameter for drug absorption in blood, drug dissolution is the rate-determining step for the oral absorption of drugs that are less water-soluble. Solubility is a crucial concern for formulation scientists to overcome. To enhance the solubility of medications, the various techniques pointed above can be used separately or in combination. Selecting the best solubility increases technique is important for getting the aim of a successful formulation, including excellent oral bioavailability, reduced dose frequency and improved patient compliance, also achieving less production cost. Nano suspension, supercritical fluid, cryogenics, particle size reduction, pH adjustment and inclusion complex formation are the most tempting methods to use among the various solubility alternatives when it comes to overcome the solubility problem of hydrophobic medications. Drug properties like solubility, chemical nature, melting point, absorption site, physical nature, pharmacokinetic behavior, etc., as well as dosage form requirements like tablet or capsule formulation, strength, immediate, or modified release, greatly impact the method of solubility enhancement. This review overall conclude that every molecule's solubility is important and play important role in development of pharmaceutical formulations.

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